

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 26**

Testing, evaluation and documentation of additional functionality of data repository service

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Abstract:

The partners in task 5.2 of the SSHOC project have developed additional functionalities for the open source Dataverse software, based on requirements of the European SSH communities. This document reports on the status of the developed functionalities.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
KNAW/DANS	Marion Wittenberg	marion.wittenberg@dans.knaw.nl
KNAW/DANS	Vyacheslav Tykhonov	vyacheslav.tykhonov@dans.knaw.nl
KNAW/DANS	Eko Indarto	eko.indarto@dans.knaw.nl
KNAW/DANS	Wilko Steinhoff	wilko.steinhoff@dans.knaw.nl
CESSDA/AUSSDA	Stefan Kasberger	stefan.kasberger@univie.ac.at
DARIAH/PSNC	Tomasz Parkoła	tparkola@man.poznan.pl
DARIAH/Universität Göttingen	Peter Kiraly	peter.kiraly@gwdg.de
CNR	Cesare Concordia	cesare.concordia@isti.cnr.it
CLARIN/University of Tromsø	Philipp Conzett	philipp.conzett@uit.no

1. Introduction

Within task 5.2 of the SSHOC project, repository software is being developed based on [Dataverse](https://dataverse.org/)¹, for the sharing and publication of research data within the Social Science and Humanities (SSH) domain. Dataverse is an open-source research data repository software developed by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS), Harvard University. More and more developers from the Dataverse community improve the software together with Harvard.

Within task 5.2 of the SSHOC project, a group of developers and research data specialists is working on functionalities to make the Dataverse repository software more compliant to the needs of the European SSH community. This document reports on the status of the developed functionalities.

¹ <https://dataverse.org/about>

2. Description of the Milestone

The Dataverse software is currently (autumn 2021) used by a community of over 70 installations among a growing number installations in European countries². Although the software fits its purpose, specific additional functionalities were needed in order for it to meet the needs of the European SSH community.

Some examples of the additional requested functionalities are: workflow to translate the Graphical User Interface to languages other than English, inclusion of metadata standards that are important to the European SSH research communities, linkage to controlled vocabularies, development of previewers, integration with CLARIN's Language Resource Switchboard, as well as deployment on cloud solutions.

During a workshop of all partners within task 5.2. on April 10, 2019 in The Hague, the preferred extra functionalities were discussed, and procedures for the development of these functionalities were established. At the workshop, developers belonging to one of the 4 main domain-specific ERICs within SSHOC (CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH and EHRIS) were represented. The discussions at the workshop resulted in Milestone 25 (MS25) 'Selection of additional functionality for data repository service to be developed'. MS25 encompasses an analysis of the preferred extra functionalities among the key stakeholders, and a selection of these based upon the broadest needs. After the workshop the

² The following 22 installations are currently available in Europe:

Austria: <https://data.aussda.at/>,

Belgium: <https://dataverse.uclouvain.be/>, <https://www.sodha.be/>,

Croatia: <https://data.crossda.hr/>,

France: <https://dataverse.cirad.fr/>, <https://data.ird.fr/>, <https://data.inrae.fr/>, <https://research-data.ifsttar.fr/>, <https://data.sciencespo.fr/dataverse/sciencespo>,

Germany: <https://data.fz-juelich.de/>, <http://data.goettingen-research-online.de/>, <https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/>, <https://darus.uni-stuttgart.de/dataverse/darus>,

Italy: <https://dataverse.unimi.it/>,

Latvia: <https://dataverse.rsu.lv/dataverse/rsu/>,

Lithuania: <https://lida.dataverse.lt>,

The Netherlands: <https://dataverse.nl>, <https://datasets.iisg.amsterdam/>,
<https://dataverse.nioz.nl/dataverse/root>,

Norway: <https://dataverse.no/>,

Poland: <https://dataverse.openforestdata.pl/>

Portugal: <https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/>,

Spain: <https://dataverse.csuc.cat/> <https://edatos.consorciomadrono.es/>,

and Russia: <https://dataverse.pushdom.ru/>

developers worked in various groups on the different functionalities. A monthly task meeting was held to monitor the progress.

The list with functionalities was updated during the project on the basis of feedback of interested stakeholders. To present our work and to collect this feedback two webinars were organised. The [first webinar](#)³ (March 18, 2020) was targeted to the CESSDA community. The [second webinar](#)⁴ (September 28, 2020), was targeted to the DARIAH community. Representatives of CLARIN provided input of the CLARIN community in separate meetings.

2.1. Role of the Milestone

This milestone reports of all the functionality developed by task 5.2 during the project and functions as the basis for Deliverable D5.5. which is due in M38.

2.2. Means of verification

Results of all development work are available on the SSHOC [Github](#)⁵. When applicable, developments are pushed to Harvard for incorporation within the master branch. Versions [4.18](#)⁶ and [5.7](#)⁷ of the master branch have functionalities developed by SSHOC task 5.2.

3. Conclusions and next steps

All developed functionalities will be finalised and documented during the last 5 months of the SSHOC project. The results will be published in D5.5.

³ Recordings and presentations available via: <https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-cessda-service-providers-dataverse>

⁴ Recordings and slides are available via: <https://sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-webinar-dariah-community-requirements-dataverse-repository> a blog about the webinars is available at: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/webinar-notes-dataverse-development-sshoc>

⁵ <https://github.com/SSHOC>

⁶ <https://dataverse.org/blog/2019/11/dataverse-418>

⁷ <https://github.com/IQSS/dataverse/releases/tag/v5.7>